

Triangulene-based frameworks for the separation of petroleum hydrocarbons

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Abstract

Triangulene-based nanostructures have been recently synthesized in great varieties demonstrating exceptional physics and chemistry. Herein we investigate perspective triangulene-based frameworks and their potential for the selective sorting of lightweight paraffins and olefins. Using first principle calculations, we scrutinize the electronic, magnetic, and optical properties of triangulene-based nanostars considered as building blocks of the frameworks. Functionalization with Fe and Cu atoms and subsequent interaction with olefins (C_2H_4 and C_3H_6) and paraffins (C_2H_6 and C_3H_8) are further considered. It is found that the nanostars successfully bind with the chosen transition metals and demonstrate positive physical and chemical adsorption of the hydrocarbons before and after functionalization. Charge transfer analysis shows that Fe-nanostars complexes are selective to alkenes, whereas Cu-nanostars complexes are selective to alkanes. The adsorption process allows for convenient tracking via UV-Vis spectrometric tools detecting a redshift as a characteristic signature of the adsorption of hydrocarbons. The reported complexes exhibit quick recovery times that insure fast bind-release cycles and therefore high gas separation performance suitable for large-scale applications.

Keywords: triangulene-based nanostars; DFT calculations; electronic, magnetic and optical properties; paraffin/olefin separation.

Environmental Implication

Porous nanostructures have shown great potential for designing chemical reaction venues for the selective binding and separation of lightweight hydrocarbons. Here we constructed novel triangulene-based frameworks for the separation of olefins and paraffins. The constructed 2D membranes show high sensitivity and selectivity, especially after attaching transition metals to the pores

41 1. Introduction

42 Crude oil has a complex composition. More precisely, it is a mixture of linear, branched, and
43 cyclic hydrocarbons referred to as paraffins and olefins. Paraffins are hydrocarbons with all
44 saturated single carbon-carbon bonds, while olefins comprise at least one non-saturated carbon-
45 carbon bond. Up to 50% of the oil constitutes hydrocarbons with lengths of carbon chains ranging
46 from 4 to 20 atoms [1]. After cracking long-chain hydrocarbons at elevated temperatures low
47 molecular weight paraffins/olefins gas mixtures are produced. Such crude oil cracking produces
48 petrochemicals, in particular ethylene, propylene, ethane, and propane [2].

49 While being important in standard petroleum chemistry production, the oil cracking and gas
50 mixture treatment also play an important role in mitigating the consequences of extreme accidents
51 such as oil spills. Accidental releases of huge amounts of oil into the natural environment face a
52 range of drastic consequences, the most important of which are environmental impacts [1,3,4] and
53 public health [5–8]. The aquatic ecosystems, particularly the marines, are the most vulnerable to
54 oil spills. The water-in-oil emulsion causes a reduction of dissolved oxygen, thereby disrupting
55 important food chains, and eventually having the potential of affecting millions of people [8]. It
56 may come as a surprise but the average time of the ecosystem recovery is 2-10 years [3]. Therefore,
57 the efficient methods of petroleum hydrocarbon treatments, including those beyond regular
58 industrial facilities, are of crucial importance.

59 The paraffins/olefins gas mixture separation normally proceeds via a low-temperature distillation,
60 extractive distillation, molecular sieving, or selective binding [9]. The distillation process is an
61 industrial-scale technology but such systems are expensive to build and operate so they are
62 economically justifiable only when high quantities of outputs are expected. Extractive distillation
63 largely relies on the properties of the polar solvent used to modify the components' relative
64 volatilities to make gas separation feasible. It has no obvious advantages over low-temperature
65 distillation. In contrast, molecular sieving with zeolites is based on equilibrium physical adsorption
66 followed by variable-temperature stepwise desorption. The energy costs of molecular sieving are
67 generally lower, but capital costs are higher than those for low-temperature distillation. Finally,
68 the usual way of selectively binding to olefins and paraffins is to use their complexation with
69 metals. Ag(I) and Cu(I) are two common choices, while other alternatives include Group VIII
70 metals such as Fe, Co, and Ni [10].

71 Porous nanostructures have shown great potential for designing chemical reaction venues for the
72 selective binding and separation of lightweight olefins from paraffins at room temperature [11–
73 14]. Metal-organic frameworks [11,12,15], porous organic cages [14], and hydrogen-bonded
74 organic frameworks [13] are among them. Recently, however, a variety of atomically precise
75 carbon nanostructures have emerged on the horizon. They have demonstrated an incredible variety
76 of edges [16–23] that had been fancied hypothetically [24–28]. The regular edges and shapes have
77 also been reported for a number of nanographenes [29–38]. Specifically, for triangular shape
78 nanographenes – the so-called triangulenes – linearly increasing sizes have been demonstrated: 3-
79 trinagulene [28], 4-triangulene [31], 5-triangulene [32], 7-trinagulene [34]. Such nanomaterials
80 exhibit open-shell structures, peculiar edge states [39–42], interesting magnetic [43–51], and
81 optical properties [39,52,53]. They, therefore, offer some desirable advantages for selective
82 binding to paraffins and olefins.

83 The self-organization processes used in atomically precise carbon nanostructures synthesis are
84 now advancing to the next level allowing the assembling of macroscopical structures out of
85 nanoprecise building blocks [54–56]. For triangulenes, it has been shown that they can be bound
86 covalently in pairs [33] and ordered into open-end chains [57] and macrocycles in the form of
87 stars [58].

88 In this paper, we use the recently synthesized triangulene-based nanostars (TNs) as the building
89 blocks of larger macrostructures – triangulene-based frameworks that are purely carbon analogs
90 of covalent organic frameworks in Ref. [55]. We explore the potential of pristine and metal-
91 coordinated (Fe and Cu) nanostars to selectively bind and separate olefins from paraffins. While
92 triangulene-based frameworks are crystal structures exhibiting translation invariance, their
93 interaction with hydrocarbon molecules is stochastic in nature, which implies breaking the
94 translation invariance. Therefore, a systematic study was carried out for the adsorption properties
95 of the crude oil cracking main products with respect to the elementary building blocks that are
96 nanostars. We found that triangulene nanostars successfully adsorb all the considered petroleum
97 hydrocarbons with moderate adsorption energy that can be significantly enhanced by attaching
98 transition metals. The nanostars show high reusability with quick recovery time. Moreover, the
99 adsorption process can be characterized by the redshift observed in the UV-Vis spectra.

100

101 **2. Computational Methodology**

102

103 The structure optimization and the physical properties of the triangulene-based nanostars are
104 investigated using the density functional theory calculations [59,60] as implemented in Gaussian
105 16 [61]. The calculations are performed using the Becke-3-parameter-Lee-Yang-Parr (B3LYP)
106 functional [62,63] and the basis set 6-31G [64,65]. This level of theory shows a good representation
107 of the electronic structure and acceptable result accuracy when compared to higher levels of theory
108 that require increased computational power [66-70]. The UV-Vis spectra are obtained by
109 performing time-dependent DFT (TD-DFT) calculations for the first twenty excited states. To
110 extend our work to include triangulene-based frameworks (infinite nanoporous sheets), we
111 perform periodic calculations using Vienna Ab-initio Simulation Package (VASP) [71,72]. All the
112 VASP calculations are performed using the projector-augmented wave method (PAW) [73]. The
113 exchange-correlation interaction is described by the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) form of the
114 generalized gradient approximation (GGA) [74]. The kinetic energy cut off for the plane wave is
115 taken to be 500 eV. To prevent the interaction of the heterostructure with its image in the
116 perpendicular direction, a vacuum spacing of 20 Å is considered. For the large supercell of 124
117 atoms, 2x2x1 Γ centered k-point sampling is used. The optimization process continues until a self-
118 consistency is obtained at an energy of 10^{-5} eV between two consecutive steps and an atomic force
119 of 10^{-4} eV/Å. The electronic properties are calculated using the B3LYP functional to be compatible
120 with Gaussian 16 calculations.

121

122

123 **3. Results and discussions**

124 The optimized structure of the triangulene-based nanostars (TNs) is shown in Fig. 1 (a). The effect
125 of attaching transition metals to the pores is considered by attaching two Fe-atoms as shown in
126 Fig. 1 (b) and two Cu-atoms, see Fig. 1 (c).

127 3.1. Structure stability

128 The binding energy (E_b) and the frequency calculations are employed to investigate the considered
129 TNs. E_b per atom is calculated from $E_b=(n_c E_c+n_H E_H+n_m E_m-E_T)/n_t$, where n_c , n_H , n_m , and n_t are the
130 total number of C, H, metal, and total number of atoms, respectively. The corresponding energies
131 are E_c , E_H , E_m , and E_t , respectively. According to this definition, a positive E_b implies a stable
132 formation of the TNs. The calculation shows that the binding energy is not only positive but also
133 has high values, namely 6.99, 6.97, and 6.96 eV for TNs, TNs-Fe, and TNs-Cu, respectively. The
134 infrared spectra shown in Fig. 1 (d-c) indicate that all the IR peaks occur at positive vibrational
135 frequencies and thus the constructed 2D membranes are dynamically stable.

136
137 Fig.1. Optimized structures (a-c) and the corresponding infrared spectra (d-f) of the triangulene-
138 based nanostars (TNs) before and after attaching Fe and Cu atoms.

139 The obtained IR spectra are in good agreement with the experimental and theoretical results
140 available in the literature [75,76]. The C-C bond length is slightly different from its value in periodic
141 2D sheets, it ranges from 1.39 Å at the edges to 1.43 Å near the pores. Also, we observe a tiny
142 curvature of the triangulenes with respect to each other.

143

144 4.2. Electronic and magnetic properties

145 Based on the partial density of states (see Fig. 2 a-c), we study the electronic properties of TN and
 146 the effect of attaching Fe and Cu atoms to them. It is observed that TNs have a semiconductor
 147 energy gap (E_g) ~ 2.1 eV with antiferromagnetic (AFM) spin ordering as shown in Fig. 2 (a). The
 148 AFM spin ordering of the nanostar is expected due to the equality between N_A and N_B atoms,
 149 where N_A/N_B is the number of atoms in sublattice A/B which agrees with Lieb's theorem [77].

150
 151 Fig. 2. (a-c) Electronic density of states of TNs, TNs-Fe, and TNs-Cu, respectively. (d-f) the
 152 corresponding spin density difference with red/blue color represents up/down spin density at
 153 isodensity value of 0.0004. (g-i) The molecular electrostatic potential for the TNs, TNs-Fe, and
 154 TNs-Cu, respectively.

155 However, since the star consists of 6 triangular nanographene with zigzag termination (ZTRI),
 156 each ZTRI has two unpaired electrons due to the inequality between N_A and N_B . Therefore, a net

157 of 12 electrons will form half-filled molecular orbitals, six with spin up and six with spin down.
158 These electronic states are localized on the edges and are highly interactive. They can be seen in
159 the partial density of states (PDOS) plot as the peaks around the energy gap that are separated from
160 other peaks, see Fig.2 (a). Their localization on single atoms can be seen in the distribution of the
161 highest occupied/lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (HOMO/LUMO) shown in Fig. S1 (a, b) in
162 Appendix A. The spin density difference of TNs is presented in Fig. 2 (d) which indicates that the
163 highest contribution to the spin-up density distributes on three triangulene while the majority of
164 spin-down density distributes on the other three triangulenes, thereby resulting the AFM spin
165 ordering.

166 Attaching Fe and Cu atoms to the TNs produces a slight change in the energy gap as in Fig. 2 (b)
167 for TNs-Fe and a moderate increase as in Fig. 2 (c) for TNs-Cu. The partial density of states shows
168 that the edge states of the TNs still form the low-energy states even after attaching Fe or Cu atoms
169 which means that these states are more interactive than the states provided by Fe or Cu. This result
170 is also observed from the HOMO and LUMO distributions shown in Fig. S1 (c-f) of Appendix A,
171 where the distributions are on the carbon atoms and not on the Fe or Cu atoms. On the other hand,
172 the attached Fe atoms transform the AFM spin ordering of TNs to ferromagnetic (FM) in the triplet
173 spin state. The increase of the net spin comes from the unpaired d-electrons of Fe atoms as seen
174 from the higher spin-up distribution around Fe in Fig. 2 (e). While the attached Cu atoms do not
175 change the magnetic state and spin density distribution shown in Fig. 2 (f) is similar to that of TNs.
176 The molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) shown in Fig. 2 (g-i) is important for identifying the
177 active sites in a certain material. It shows a color scheme for the charge distribution on the TNs
178 where a red color means electron-rich regions (electrophilic sites); blue colors are hole-rich sites
179 (nucleophilic sites). Light blue, yellow, and green are intermediate regions with slight positive,
180 slightly negative, and neutral charges. The red and yellow colors distributed on the surface and the
181 edges of the star, see Fig. 2 (g, h), indicate that these regions are rich in electrons and can act as
182 electrophilic attackers. While the blue regions around the H-atoms at the edges and the pores
183 suggest electrophilic attacks at these sites. The case of TNs-Cu is different since the whole star has
184 a positively charged distribution with the maximum on the Cu atoms.

185 To extend our study to infinite sheets from TNs, we present in Fig. S2 (Appendix B) the results
186 obtained from periodic calculations. In Fig. S2 (a) we show the supercell used to construct the
187 triangulene-based framework (TFs, see Fig. S2 (b)). We found that the band gap of the TFs
188 decreases to 1.66 eV for the spin-up and 1.67 eV for the spin-down energy states. This decrease is
189 mainly a result of decreasing the quantum size effect by increasing the size of the structure. The
190 density of states shown in Fig. S2 (c) indicates that the electronic density peaks of spin up and spin
191 down have almost the same energies and distributions, which is similar to that of TNs. The spin
192 density difference shown in Fig. S2 (d) shows that for each TNs, the spin-up density distributes on
193 three triangulenes and the spin-down distributes on the other three which is similar to the finite
194 TNs in Fig. 2 (d). The effect of chemical modification is also considered in periodic calculations
195 by attaching four Cu or Fe atoms to the supercell to construct the TFs-metal complex shown in
196 Fig. S3 (b, d). Therefore, the structural, electronic, and magnetic properties of functionalized TFs
197 are just an extension of the finite TNs-metals and some differences should be expected. For
198 instance, the energy gaps experience a moderate decrease in TFs-Fe, $E_{g\alpha}/E_{g\beta}=1.32/1.21$ eV. While

199 in the case of TFs-Cu, the gaps significantly decrease to $E_{g\alpha}/E_{g\beta}=0.81/0.61$ eV which is almost
200 one-third of the gap before complexation with Cu-atoms. Similar to TFs, TFs-Cu has
201 antiferromagnetic spin ordering with a net magnetic moment equal to zero. The only difference
202 in the spin density distribution, see Fig. S3, is the order of the triangulenes on which the spin up
203 and spin down density distributes, as seen in Fig. S3 (b). On the other hand, TFs-Fe is a
204 ferromagnetic structure with a net magnetic moment equal to 2. The spin density difference in Fig.
205 S3 (d) shows that the net spin comes from two Fe atoms that aligned together to produce two spin-
206 down unpaired electrons, see the encircled atoms in Fig. S3 (d). While the d-orbital electrons of
207 the other two Fe atoms aligned to form antiferromagnetic ordering, see the arrows in Fig. S3 (d).

208 3.3. Adsorption of hydrocarbons

209 The adsorption of different hydrocarbons metals is investigated before and after attaching
210 transition metals to TNs. We consider the adsorption of C_2H_4 and C_3H_6 as examples of olefins and
211 C_2H_6 and C_3H_8 as examples of paraffins. The adsorption process started by placing the olefins and
212 paraffins at 3.5 Å above the edge and pore of TNs then the optimization is performed, Fig. 3 (a-c)
213 shows the optimized structures for selected cases. It is observed that C_2H_4 is physically adsorbed
214 on the edge (Fig. 3 a) and the pore (Fig. 3 b) at adsorption lengths of 2.99 Å and 2.69 Å,
215 respectively. Other hydrocarbons are also adsorbed physically on the edges or the pores of the
216 pristine TNs with adsorption lengths from 2.53 to 3.03 Å, see Table 1. The values of the adsorption
217 energy in Table 1 confirm that TNs physically adsorb heavy metals with adsorption energies
218 ranging from -0.22 to -0.39 eV. The adsorption energy (E_a) is given by the ground state energy
219 difference between the products and the reactants, thus negative values indicate successful
220 adsorption of the heavy metals. Even with moderate physical adsorption, the molecular orbitals
221 formed by the adsorbed molecules are more stable than the molecular orbitals of the edge states of
222 TNs. This is observed from the HOMO and LUMO distributions on the TNs not on the C_2H_4 as
223 seen in Fig. 3 (d, e). The contribution of C_2H_4 to the density of states can be seen in Fig. 3 (f)
224 where its black peaks can be found deeper in the PDOS spectra.

225

226 Fig. 3. The optimized structures showing the adsorption of C₂H₄ on the edge (a), the pore (b), and edge
 227 adsorption of C₃H₈ (f) by the pristine TNs. (d, e) The spin up HOMO and LUMO distributions of the
 228 complexes in (a) and (b), respectively. (f-h) PDOS of selected complexes before (f) and after attaching Fe
 229 (g) and Cu (h). (i, j) Selected spin up molecular orbitals distributions for TNs-Fe-C₂H₄ and TNs-C₃H₈.

230

231 Table 1. The adsorption length (L), the adsorption energy (E_a) of hydrocarbons and the spin up/down
 232 energy gaps (E_{gα}/ E_{gβ}) of the complexes.

complex	L (Å)	E _a (eV)	E _{gα} / E _{gβ} (eV)	complex	L(Å)	E _a (eV)	E _{gα} / E _{gβ} (eV)
TNs-C ₂ H ₄ -p	2.53	-0.23	2.04/2.00	TNs-Fe-C ₂ H ₄ -p	2.05	-2.03	1.34/1.29

TNs-C ₂ H ₆ -p	2.90	-0.22	2.03/2.05	TNs-Fe-C ₂ H ₆ -p	2.50	-0.69	1.58/1.52
TNs-C ₃ H ₆ -p	2.87	-0.39	2.04/2.03	TNs-Fe-C ₃ H ₆ -p	2.05	-1.62	1.39/1.41
TNs-C ₃ H ₈ -p	2.58	-0.32	2.05/2.02	TNs-Fe-C ₃ H ₈ -p	2.59	-0.74	1.52/1.62
TNs -C ₂ H ₄ -e	2.92	-0.22	2.05/2.03	TNs-Cu-C ₂ H ₄ -p	2.02	-1.93	1.74/1.79
TNs -C ₂ H ₆ -e	3.03	-0.23	2.05/2.04	TNs-Cu-C ₂ H ₆ -p	1.7	-0.84	1.54/1.78
TNs -C ₃ H ₆ -e	2.93	-0.39	2.04/2.05	TNs-Cu-C ₃ H ₆ -p	2.01	-2.13	1.67/1.78
TNs -C ₃ H ₈ -e	2.94	-0.34	2.05/2.02	TNs-Cu-C ₃ H ₈ -p	1.68	-0.93	1.59/1.80

233

234 Attaching transition metals to the pores of TNs significantly enhances the adsorption process with
 235 a noticeable decrease/increase in the adsorption length/energy. The adsorption length as listed in
 236 Table 1, seen in Fig. 3 (i, j) decreases in some cases to 1.7 Å as in TNs-Cu-C₂H₆-p. The decrease
 237 is a result of the strong attraction of the hydrocarbons by the metals that moves the hydrocarbon
 238 to the pores near the metal as seen in Fig. 3 (i, j). Metals also transform the adsorption to the region
 239 of chemical adsorption with adsorption energy ranging from 0.7 eV to 2.1 eV. It is noted from
 240 Table 1 that in some cases confusion about the inverse proportionality between the adsorption
 241 length (L) and the adsorption energy may appear. For instance, L for TNs-Cu-C₃H₆-p and TNs-
 242 Cu-C₃H₈-p is 2.01 Å and 1.68 Å thus the form should have lower adsorption. However, this is not
 243 the case because we take L as the minimum distance between any atom in the hydrocarbon and
 244 the TNs which is C-atom (that forms the chemical bond with TNs) in the first case and H-atom in
 245 the second case. The PDOS in Fig. 3 (g) shows that the intensity of C₂H₄ peaks increases after
 246 attaching Fe. The corresponding molecular orbital is also deeper in the valence band like before
 247 attaching Fe, as seen in Fig. 3 (i) for the HOMO and HOMO-10 distributions. The same is observed
 248 for the density of states of the adsorbed C₃H₈ by TNs-Cu as shown in Fig. 3 (h, j). The effect of
 249 hydrocarbon adsorption on the spin up/ down energy gaps ($E_{g\alpha}/E_{g\beta}$) is listed in Table 1. The values
 250 show a slight effect in cases of physical adsorption with $E_g \sim 2.0$ - 2.05 eV which is almost the same
 251 as E_g before adsorption. In the cases of Fe and Cu-modified TNs, the changes are more prominent,
 252 especially for TNs-Cu.

253

254 3.4 Charge transfer analysis

255

256 The study utilized the B3LYP/6-31G level of theory to compute the natural atomic charge,
 257 natural population, and natural electronic configuration of carbon atoms in hydrocarbons, namely
 258 C₂H₄, C₂H₆, C₃H₆, and C₃H₈, both before and after adsorption on TNs and TNs-metal. Results
 259 presented in Tables 2 and 3 demonstrate that the negative natural charge on carbon atoms of
 260 adsorbed hydrocarbons in all studied complexes is greater compared to hydrocarbons before
 261 adsorption. This is attributed to carbon in TNs compounds donating charge to the hydrocarbons,
 262 including C₂H₄, C₂H₆, C₃H₆, and C₃H₈, indicating a higher electron transfer from the C-donor in
 263 TNs to the adsorbed hydrocarbons. Moreover, when TNs are functionalized with transition metals
 264 such as Cu and Fe, the negative formal charge of the carbon of the adsorbed hydrocarbons
 265 increases compared to TNs without the metals, confirming that Fe and Cu enhance the adsorption
 266 of hydrocarbons on TNs. Furthermore, electronic configurations for carbon atoms in adsorbed

267 hydrocarbons in all TNs-based compounds were provided. It is observed that C₂H₄, C₃H₆, and
 268 C₃H₈ hydrocarbons bind with TNs and TNs-metal through the 2s, 2p, and 3p orbitals, while C₂H₆
 269 links via the 2s and 2p orbitals. Table 3 shows that the negative formal charge of C191 was more
 270 elevated in both TNs-Fe-C₂H₄-p and TNs-Fe-C₃H₆-p than in TNs-Cu-C₂H₄-p and TNs-Cu-C₃H₆-
 271 p. Conversely, in TNs-Cu-C₂H₆-p and TNs-Cu-C₃H₈-p, the negative formal charge of C191 was
 272 higher compared to TNs-Fe-C₂H₆-p and TNs-Fe-C₃H₈-p. Hence, Fe-modification is favorable for
 273 the adsorption of olefins like ethylene and propene, whereas Cu-modification is favorable for the
 274 adsorption of paraffins like ethane and propane.

275

276 Table 2. Natural charge, population, and electronic configuration for hydrocarbons before adsorption.

Compound	Target atom	Natural charge	Core	Valence	Rydberg	Total	Natural electronic configuration
C ₂ H ₄	C	-0.44036	1.99910	4.43138	0.00989	6.44036	[core]2S(1.07)2p(3.36)3p(0.01)
C ₂ H ₆	C	-0.68462	1.99934	4.68266	0.00262	6.68462	[core]2S(1.10)2p(3.59)
C ₃ H ₆	Middle C	-0.20676	1.99909	4.19696	0.01071	6.20676	[core]2S(1.00)2p(3.20)3p(0.01)
C ₃ H ₈	Middle C	-0.55286	1.99894	4.54530	0.00862	6.55286	[core]2S(0.94)2p(3.61)3p(0.01)

277

278

279

Table 3. Natural charge, population, and electronic configuration for complexes.

Complexes	Target atom	Natural charge	Natural population				Natural electronic configuration
			Core	Valence	Rydberg	Total	
TNs-C ₂ H ₄ -p	C193	-0.44558	1.99909	4.43568	0.01081	6.44558	[core]2S ^(1.07) 2p ^(3.37) 3p ^(0.01)
TNs-C ₂ H ₆ -p	C193	-0.69748	1.99933	4.69458	0.00358	6.69748	[core]2S ^(1.10) 2p ^(3.59)
TNs-C ₃ H ₆ -p	C193	-0.21337	1.99900	4.20294	0.01143	6.21337	[core]2S ^(0.98) 2p ^(3.23) 3p ^(0.01)
TNs-C ₃ H ₈ -p	C193	-0.46381	1.99922	4.45893	0.00566	6.46381	[core]2S ^(1.04) 2p ^(3.42) 3p ^(0.01)
TNs-C ₂ H ₄ -e	C193	-0.43974	1.99909	4.43051	0.01014	6.43974	[core]2S ^(1.06) 2p ^(3.37) 3p ^(0.01)
TNs-C ₂ H ₆ -e	C193	-0.69682	1.99933	4.69381	0.00368	6.69682	[core]2S ^(1.10) 2p ^(3.59)
TNs-C ₃ H ₆ -e	C193	-0.21400	1.99900	4.20346	0.01154	6.21400	[core]2S ^(0.98) 2p ^(3.23) 3p ^(0.01)
TNs-C ₃ H ₈ -e	C193	-0.46357	1.99922	4.45832	0.00603	6.46357	[core]2S ^(1.04) 2p ^(3.42) 3p ^(0.01)
TNs-Fe-C ₂ H ₄ -p	C191	-0.69462	1.99914	4.67725	0.01822	6.69462	[core]2S ^(1.10) 2p ^(3.57) 3p ^(0.01)
TNs-Fe-C ₂ H ₆ -p	C191	-0.68344	1.99934	4.68079	0.00332	6.68344	[core]2S ^(1.10) 2p ^(3.58)
TNs-Fe-C ₃ H ₆ -p	C191	-0.44464	1.99902	4.42538	0.02024	6.44464	[core]2S ^(1.02) 2p ^(3.41) 3p ^(0.02)
TNs-Fe-C ₃ H ₈ -p	C191	-0.45321	1.99923	4.44852	0.00545	6.45321	[core]2S ^(1.03) 2p ^(3.42)
TNs-Cu-C ₂ H ₄ -p	C191	-0.61359	1.99910	4.59110	0.02340	6.61359	[core]2S ^(1.09) 2p ^(3.50) 3p ^(0.02)
TNs-Cu-C ₂ H ₆ -p	C191	-0.77179	1.99930	4.74918	0.02332	6.77179	[core]2S ^(1.10) 2p ^(3.65) 3p ^(0.02)
TNs-Cu-C ₃ H ₆ -p	C191	-0.35953	1.99898	4.33494	0.02560	6.35953	[core]2S ^(1.01) 2p ^(3.33) 3S ^(0.01) 3p ^(0.02)
TNs-Cu-C ₃ H ₈ -p	C191	-0.52160	1.99920	4.50421	0.01819	6.52160	[core]2S ^(1.04) 2p ^(3.46) 3p ^(0.02)

280 3.5. Optical properties

281 The TD/ B3LYP/6-31G approach was used in this paper to determine the computational electronic
282 UV-Vis absorption spectra for TNs and its based forms of TNs-Cu, TNs-Fe, TNs-Cu-C₂H₄, and
283 TNs-Fe-C₂H₄. The findings are displayed in Fig. 4 with the relevant parameters listed in Table 4.
284 The calculated electronic absorption spectrum of TNs, TNs -Cu, TNs-Fe, TNs-Cu-C₂H₄, and TNs-
285 Fe-C₂H₄ appears as three transitions. The electronic transitions for TNs have been observed at
286 wavelengths of 755.96, 753.54, and 740.00 nm, while for TNs-Cu, the transitions occur at 890.06,
287 888.70, and 776.00 nm. TNs-Fe exhibits transitions at wavelengths of 942.98, 1096.00, and
288 1103.19 nm, and TNs-Cu-C₂H₄ at wavelengths of 931.14, 860.00, and 843.85 nm. Finally, TNs-
289 Fe-C₂H₄ transitions occur at wavelengths 1022.23, 1026.69, and 1127.00 nm. According to Fig. 4,
290 the maximum absorption wavelengths for TNs, TNs -Cu, TNs-Fe, TNs-Cu-C₂H₄, and TNs-Fe-
291 C₂H₄ are 740.00, 776.00, 1096.00, 860.00, and 1127.00 nm, respectively. These wavelengths
292 correspond to the electronic transitions H→L+1, H-2→L+1, H→L+1, H→L, and H-1→L+1,
293 respectively. Compared to TNs, the dominant absorption peaks for TNs-Cu, TNs-Fe, TNs-Cu-
294 C₂H₄, and TNs-Fe-C₂H₄ are red-shifted and exhibit 2-3 fold increase in the intensity. This indicates
295 that the binding of transition metals (Fe and Cu) to the TNs and the adsorption of petroleum
296 hydrocarbons can be detected by comparing UV-Vis spectra before and after these interactions.
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299 Fig. 4 Calculated absorption spectra of TNs, TNs-Cu, TNs-Fe, TNs-Cu-C₂H₄ and TNs-Fe-C₂H₄.

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Table 4. Calculated electronic absorption of TNs, TNs-Cu, TNs-Fe, TNs-Cu-C₂H₄, and TNs-Fe-C₂H₄.

TD-Computational				
TNs				
Excited state	Electronic transitions	ΔE (eV)	f	Coefficient
1	H -> L	1.6401 (755.96nm)	0.0003	0.05354
	H-3 -> L+1			0.60134
2	H -> L	1.6454(753.54nm)	0.0046	0.12196
	H-1 -> L+1			-0.11753
3	H -> L+1	1.6565(740.00nm)	0.0195	0.11204
	H-1 -> L			0.11507
TNs-Cu				
1	H -> L	1.3930(890.06nm)	0.0069	0.77089
	H -> L+2			0.57658
2	H -> L+3	1.3951(888.70nm)	0.0013	0.57658
	H -> L+1			0.77089
3	H -2-> L+1	1.6556(776.0nm)	0.0219	0.29155
	H-3-> L			0.29155
TNs-Fe				
1	H-4 -> L+8	1.3096(942.98nm)	0.0024	0.10940
	H-7 -> L+9			0.23664
2	H-> L+1	1.2215(1096nm)	0.0336	0.46581
	H-2 -> L			0.70310
3	H-> L	1.1239(1103.19nm)	0.0016	0.72054
	H -> L+1			0.16943
TNs-Cu-C ₂ H ₄				
1	H -> L+2	1.3315(931.14nm)	0.0036	0.63370
	H -> L			0.72228
2	H -> L+2	1.3931(860.00nm)	0.0075	0.59140
	H -> L			0.74984
3	H -> L	1.4693(843.85nm)	0.0001	0.66298
	H -> L+2			0.72220
TNs-Fe-C ₂ H ₄				
1	H -> L+5	1.2129(1022.23nm)	0.0010	0.55771
	H -> L+7			0.82906
2	H-1 -> L+1	1.2076(1026.69nm)	0.0011	0.10374
	H-5 -> L			0.95374
3	H-1 -> L+1	1.1242(1127.00nm)	0.1059	0.71676
	H-3 -> L			0.67921

330 3.6 Reusability

331 reusable separator device must have a quick recovery time, which is accomplished by either exposing
332 UV radiation or heating it to a high temperature. We utilized the following equation $\tau =$
333 $\nu^{-1} e^{-E_{\text{ads.}}/K_{\text{B}}T}$ to estimate the recovery time for our proposed models. Where ν^{-1} is the attempt frequency,
334 $E_{\text{ads.}}$ is the adsorption energy, K_{B} is Boltzmann's constant in eV, and T is the temperature. For our work,
335 attempt frequency value of 10^{-12}s^{-1} was chosen [78]. Table 4 displays the recovery times for both TNs and
336 TNs-metal complex forms. The calculated recovery times for all the complexes are listed in the following
337 sequence: TNs-hydrocarbon followed by TNs-metal-hydrocarbon. Based on this order, it can be inferred
338 the presence of a metal functional group increases the recovery time. However, upon analyzing the
339 values in Table 4, it is observed that all the investigated complexes exhibit high reusability.

340

341 Table 4. Computed recovery time τ (s) of TNs and TNs-heavy metals complex forms.

Complex	τ (s)	Complex	τ (s)
TNs-C2H4-p	6.00×10^{-12}	TNs-Fe-C2H4-p	7.35×10^{-06}
TNs-C2H6-p	5.55×10^{-12}	TNs-Fe-C2H6-p	2.16×10^{-10}
TNs-C3H6-p	2.09×10^{-11}	TNs-Fe-C3H6-p	3.02×10^{-07}
TNs-C3H8-p	1.21×10^{-11}	TNs-Fe-C3H8-p	3.18×10^{-10}
TNs-C2H4-e	5.55×10^{-12}	TNs-Cu-C2H4-p	3.37×10^{-06}
TNs-C2H6-e	6.00×10^{-12}	TNs-Cu-C2H6-p	6.94×10^{-10}
TNs-C3H6-e	2.09×10^{-11}	TNs-Cu-C3H6-p	1.60×10^{-05}
TNs-C3H8-e	1.41×10^{-11}	TNs-Cu-C3H8-p	1.40×10^{-09}

342

343 4. Conclusion

344 In summary, the electronic, magnetic, and optical properties of triangulene-based nanostars before
345 and after attaching Fe and Cu atoms have been investigated using density functional theory
346 calculations. Their capability to separate light hydrocarbons has also been investigated. The
347 nanostars are antiferromagnetic systems with almost the same spin up/down energy gap of ~ 2.1
348 eV. Periodic calculations show that the frameworks from these nanostars are also
349 antiferromagnetic spin ordered but with lower energy gaps of ~ 1.7 eV. Attaching two Fe-atoms to
350 the pores transforms the nanostar into a ferromagnetic system in the triplet spin state while
351 attaching Cu-atoms keeps the antiferromagnetic state unchanged. The energy gap decreases in the
352 two cases from that of the pristine nanostar with a noticeable difference between spin-up and spin-
353 down energy gaps. The partial density of states shows that the low energy orbitals are mainly from
354 the interactive edge states that make the nanostars suitable for hydrocarbon adsorption. With
355 moderate adsorption energy, the nanostars are capable of adsorbing light olefins (C_2H_4 and C_3H_6)
356 and paraffins (C_2H_6 and C_3H_8). The adsorption was significantly enhanced by attaching Fe or Cu
357 with the preferable adsorption of olefins by Fe-modified nanostar and the preferable adsorption of
358 paraffins by Cu-modified one. The UV-vis spectra show a redshift after attaching transition metals
359 and hydrocarbon adsorption which can help in the characterization process. The calculated quick
360 recovery time, from 6×10^{-11} to 1.5×10^{-5} (s), ensures high reusability. These results suggest that

361 the triangulene-based frameworks are performant, selective, and reusable 2D membranes for the
362 removal of petroleum hydrocarbons.

363 Appendix A

364 In this section, we present the distribution of the HOMO and LUMO of the TNs in Fig. S1 (a, b)
365 before attaching transition metals and after attachment of Fe (c, d) and Cu (e, f) for spin up and
366 spin down electrons. The localized distribution of HOMO and LUMO on single atoms at the
367 zigzag edges indicates that they originate from unpaired C-atoms at the edges. It is also observed
368 that even after attaching Fe or Cu atoms at the pore edges, The HOMO and LUMO are still mainly
369 contributed by these edge states. Therefore, these interactive states are expected to have a
370 significant impact on the adsorption and catalytic properties of TNs.

371

373 Fig. S1. The HOMO and LUMO distributions of the spin up and spin down electrons for TNs (a, b), TNs-
374 Fe (c, d), and for TNs-Cu (e, f).

375 **Appendix B**

376 The results from the periodic calculations of the extended triangulene-based frameworks (TFs) are
377 presented here. The supercell and the corresponding CFs are shown in Fig S2 (a) and (b),
378 respectively. The electronic density of states of the antiferromagnetic spin-ordered TFs are shown
379 in Fig. S2 (c) and the spin density difference is shown in Fig. S2 (d). The effect of attaching
380 transition metals to the pores of TFs is shown in Fig. S3, where the electronic density of states and
381 the spin density differences are given for TFs-Cu and TFs-Fe, respectively.

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383
384 Fig. S2. (a) The supercell used to build the extended triangulene-based frameworks (TFs). (b) a
385 part from the TFs consists of five TNs. (c, d) the density of states of TFs and the corresponding
386 spin density difference.

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391 Fig. S3. The density of states and the spin density after attaching Cu (a, b) and Fe (c, d) atoms.

392

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